

3-(6-Substituted-2-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-5-substituted-1-morpholinomethyl-2-indolinones (4): To 3-(6-substituted-2-hydrazonobenzothiazolyl)-5-substituted-2-indolinone (0.005 mol) suspended in hot DMF (20.0 ml), were added 40% formaldehyde (0.5 ml) and morpholine (0.5 ml) and the reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath till a clear solution resulted. The solid product separated on keeping the solution overnight, was filtered under suction, washed several times with methanol and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (Table 1).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Head, Chemistry Department for facilities. The authors are grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance. Thanks are also due to Dr. R. S. Kapil and Prof. S. P. Singh for analytical/spectral data.

References

1. L. KATZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4007.
2. G. S. MARVEL and G. S. HIRRS, *Org. Synth.*, 1941, 1, 321.
3. I. A. KHAN, Ph.D. Thesis, Lucknow University, 1977.
4. J. HARLEY-MASON and R. F. J. INGLEBY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3639.

A Few 2-(Substituted-acetyl)-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles as CNS Depressants

PRADEEP MISHRA*, ASHOK K. SHAKYA

and

R. K. AGRAWAL

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Doctor Hari Singh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

and

G. K. PATNAIK

Division of Pharmacology,
Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow-226 001

Manuscript received 22 July 1988, revised 2 November 1989,
accepted 5 February 1990

COMPOUNDS containing 1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus have been reported to possess various biological activities¹, when properly substituted at 2- or 5-position of the ring.

In continuation of our earlier work on 1,3,4-thiadiazoles as CNS depressants², the title compounds were prepared and evaluated for CNS depressant activity. Condensation of thiosemicarbazide (1) with aliphatic acid in presence of sulphuric acid gave 2-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (2). Acetylation of 2 with chloroacetyl chloride and condensation with the appropriate amine yielded 2-(substituted-acetyl)amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (4).

All the compounds showed characteristic IR bands at 3 450–3 300 (NH), 1 700–1 680 (C=O), 1 210, 1 075, 980 and 825 cm^{-1} (1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus).

Experimental

All the compounds were routinely checked by tlc on silica gel-G using ethanol-acetic acid-water (5 : 3 : 2) for purity. IR spectra (KBr) of compounds were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. The melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected.

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (2) : The compounds were prepared³ using thiosemicarbazide (1; 0.125 mol), aliphatic acid (0.150 mol) and concentrated sulphuric acid (25 ml) : 2a (R = methyl) (65%), m.p. 228–30° (lit. 230°), yield 65%; 2b (R = ethyl) (80%), 192–94° (lit. 194°); 2c (R = propyl) (80%) 202–04° (lit. 204°).

2-Chloroacetylamino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3) : To compound 2 (0.10 mol) dissolved in dioxane (25 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.10 mol) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h. On adding the mixture to ice-cold distilled water, a solid product was obtained which was recrystallisation from ethanol (95%, v/v) : 3a (R = methyl) (90%), m.p. 235–36° (lit. 236°); 3b (R = ethyl) (80%), 224–26° (lit. 226°); 3c (R = propyl) (85%) 206–08° (lit. 208°).

2-(Substituted-acetyl)amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4) : A mixture of 3 (0.02 mol), appropriate amine (0.04–0.05 mol) and benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 4–5 h. The amine hydrochloride which crystallised out on cooling was filtered off. The filtrate was extracted several times with hydrochloric acid (1N). The combined acid extracts were made alkaline with sodium hydroxide (1N) and extracted with diethyl ether several times. The ether extracts were combined and the solvent distilled off to get crude product which was recrystallised from ethanol (90%, v/v) (Table 1).

Biological studies : The drug solutions (100 mg ml^{-1}) of the compounds were prepared in normal saline. The approximate lethal dose (ALD_{50}) was determined in mice intraperitoneally (i.p.) by the reported method⁴. The effect on gross behaviour pattern, response to touch, pain and sound, sedation,

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF DATA COMPOUNDS (4)*

Code no.	R	X	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Biological activity**			
						ALD ₅₀ (mg/kg)	SMA	Loss of R.R.	
AK-1	Methyl	Dimethylamino	C ₇ H ₁₂ SN ₄ O	186–87	83	>1 000	214	157	–
AK-2	Ethyl	Dimethylamino	C ₉ H ₁₄ SN ₄ O	78–80	80	>1 000	207	142	+
AK-3	Propyl	Dimethylamino	C ₉ H ₁₆ SN ₄ O	160–62	75	681	205	139	+
AK-4	Methyl	Diethylamino	C ₉ H ₁₆ SN ₄ O	200–02	78	681	213	141	–
AK-5	Ethyl	Diethylamino	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ SN ₄ O	185–87	86	681	209	148	+
AK-6	Propyl	Diethylamino	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ SN ₄ O	160–62	68	681	200	140	+
AK-7	Methyl	Dipropylamino	C ₁₁ H ₂₀ SN ₄ O	130–32	72	681	208	144	–
AK-8	Ethyl	Dipropylamino	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ SN ₄ O	148–50	70	1 000	210	110	++
AK-9	Propyl	Dipropylamino	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ SN ₄ O	135–37	69	681	210	115	++
AK-10	Methyl	Dibutylamino	C ₁₃ H ₂₄ SN ₄ O	152–54	75	681	210	140	+
AK-11	Ethyl	Dibutylamino	C ₁₄ H ₂₆ SN ₄ O	100–02	63	1 000	214	139	+
AK-12	Propyl	Dibutylamino	C ₁₅ H ₂₈ SN ₄ O	87–89	59	562	210	144	+
AK-13	Methyl	4-Morpholino	C ₉ H ₁₄ SN ₄ O ₂	160–62	65	>1 000	210	140	+
AK-14	Ethyl	4-Morpholino	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ SN ₄ O ₂	206–08	68	562	216	146	+
AK-15	Propyl	4-Morpholino	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ SN ₄ O ₂	139–41	75	681	210	150	+

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N percentage.

**Administered dose was 1/5th of ALD₅₀; (+)=Moderate effect, (++)=strong effect, (–)=no effect; SMA=spontaneous motor activity, RR=righting reflex.

righting reflexes, spontaneous motor activity (SMA) were recorded following the reported method⁶. Only the compounds showing encouraging effect that is AK-8 and AK-9 were further studied for their effect on pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis in rats following the literature method⁶. The compounds were also studied for anticonvulsant activity using both chemical⁷ and maximal electro-shock method⁸. Results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The ALD₅₀ of compounds were found in the range 562–1000 mg/kg (intraperitoneally). All the compounds showed some depressant effect on the studies on gross behaviour except AK-1, AK-4, AK-7 which showed some stimulant effect. The depressant effects shown by AK-8 and AK-9 were noteworthy and hence pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis study was undertaken. The increase in pentobarbitone-induced hypnosis was found to be 50.81 and 39.48% for AK-8 and AK-9 respectively. None of the compounds was found to be anticonvulsant.

Acknowledgement

Authors wish to thank the Head, Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Doctor Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar and Head, Division of Pharmacology, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for facilities. Thanks are also due to Head, RSIC, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, for spectral and elemental analysis data. One of the authors (A.K.S) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- J. S. SHUKLA, M. SINGH and R. RASTOGI *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, **22**, 206; R. O. TWEIT, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **79**, 78813; M. I. HUSAIN, A. KUMAR and R. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1986, **55**, 644; O. B. CHAPLEO, P. L. MYERS, A. C. B. SMITH, J. F. TULLOCH and D. C. WALTER, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1987, **30**, 951; V. K. PANDEY, H. C. LOHANI and A. K. AGARWAL, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1982, **44**, 155; V. H. SHAH, H. H. PATEL and A. R. PARIKH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 678; S. GIRI and H. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 175.
- P. MISHRA, U. M. REDDY and R. K. AGRAWAL, *J. Inst. Chem., Calcutta*, 1989, **61**, 31.
- G. FUNATSUKURI and M. UEDA, *Jap. Pat.* 20 944/1960 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1967, **66**, 46490).
- H. J. HORN, *Biometrics*, 1966, **22**, 311.
- S. PRASAD and C. O. MALHOTRA, *Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 1968, **12**, 175.
- P. C. DANDIYA and H. CULLUMBINE, *J. Pharmacol. Expt. Therap.*, 1959, **125**, 353.
- E. A. SWINYARD, W. C. BROWN and L. S. GOODMAN, *J. Pharmacol. Expt. Therap.*, 1952, **106**, 319.
- I. F. TULLOCH, D. S. WALTER, G. M. HOWE and S. J. HOWE, *Neuropharmacol.*, 1982, **21**, 555.

Synthesis of some 1-Arylthioanilido-4-aryl-3-methyl-6-imino-4,7-dihydropyrazolo-[5,4-d]-1,3-thiazines as Potential Pesticides

NIRUPAMA TIWARI, BANDANA DWIVEDI,

ROAB ALI and NIZAMUDDIN*

Department of Chemistry, University of Gorakhpur,
Gorakhpur-273 009

Manuscript received 8 August 1989, revised 17 October 1989,
accepted 5 February 1990

In continuation of our work on fused heterocycles¹ and in view of the activities exhibited by pyrazole² and thiazine³ rings, we thought it of interest to couple these biolabile rings together with the hope